

HISTORICAL ARTISTIC WORKS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATIONAL AND ANALYTICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR

Siddikov Ilyasjon Bakhromovich

Professor of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10440611>

Abstract

In this article, it is necessary to develop the informational and analytical competence of future history teachers through the assimilation of the main scientific evidence of history from historical sources and manuals, and through historical-artistic works, through a more complete and deep understanding of its essence and importance.

Key words: national development, new thinking, informational and analytical skills, future history teachers, competence, historical and artistic works, historical evidence, primary and secondary sources.

INTRODUCTION

Today, on the basis of the idea of national progress, the achievement of social development, the formation of the historical consciousness of society is taking place on the basis of the rich historical heritage of our great ancestors. It is possible to literally form the spiritual image of young people only by studying such a great heritage. Such heritage can be mastered through history. Because without studying such a heritage, it is impossible to successfully complete the reforms that are being implemented today.

In Uzbekistan, the attitude towards the science of history has risen to the level of state policy. The importance of impartial and scientifically thorough study of the history of our country with a new way of thinking, relying on primary sources in its analysis is becoming more and more necessary. This puts serious tasks before historians. Speaking about this problem, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized the importance of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism and national pride, for this, it is important to teach history well, to expand scientific research in this direction, and he says, among other things: "National history should be created with a national spirit. . Akshol has no educational influence. We need to teach our youth to learn from history, draw conclusions, arm them with the science of history, historical thinking" [1:288].

"History endures everything. But he cannot bear to falsify himself" [5:34]. After all, the study of history sharpens our thinking, allows us to be proud of the history of the past, and to be free from the mistakes made in the future.

"Studying history," said the great German enlightener of the 18th century, Friedrich Schiller, "illuminates our minds and ignites our hearts with noble devotion." He protects our soul from treating moral issues with humility and pettiness" [8:83-84].

The task of the science of history is not to teach the students dry numbers and chronicles, on the contrary, by mastering its content, to enable young people to independently understand social phenomena, to actively and creatively participate in all areas of the development of our country, and in general to acquire informational and analytical skills. should consist of preparation. This task, based on its nature, requires the development of thinking, the ability of the student to independently understand the studied event and the events of modern society. Without this, it is impossible to evaluate them correctly, to direct one's relations to the necessary actions. That is why the development of informational and analytical competence in future history teachers represents the main condition and means of history education. Here we are talking about the fact that in the process of teaching "History" students can perceive our long-term past as a whole, understand its essence and be able to evaluate it objectively. Because in-depth study of these subjects allows students to correctly perceive historical reality, to understand it, to teach them to think on this basis, and to develop historical-analytical thinking in a person as a whole.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In modern conditions, scientific-research works on the development of informational-analytical competence are carried out in philosophical, psychological-pedagogical and methodical directions. Uzbek scientists O.G. Davlatov, A.F. Ismailov, Q.R. Shonazarov conducted scientific research on the preparation of future history teachers for the formation of historical thinking in students and methodological preparation. B.A. Abdikarimov, A.M. Abdirov, G.D. Baubekova, V.I. Andreyev, S.D. Yakusheva, I.A. Zyazyuna, N.N. Nikitina, G.V. Bragina, V.V. Davidov, V.YE. Jabakov, L.V. Zanina, N.P. Menshikov, M.V. Korepanova, I.D. Lushnikova, I.P. Rachenko, V.P. Simonov, N.N. Tarasevich, I.F. Krivonos, S.B. Yelkanov, Y.N. Kuliutkin, organization of scientific creativity of learners, continuous have developed effective methods for the development of the process of scientific creativity in the professional education system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When it comes to the development of informational and analytical competence of future history teachers, it is impossible not to turn to historical and artistic

works. As A. Ibrahimov emphasized this point in his pamphlet "We are Uzbeks...Reflections on the foundations of our national statehood", "True, the science of history describes the reality of the past with concrete evidence, relying on sources. However, when it comes to the formation of a person's worldview, it can be cited as an example that achieving this is more clearly described in the works of the writer O. Balzac than in scientific literature" [2:8]. For this reason, in the development of informational-analytical competence of future history teachers, one cannot neglect fiction. Historical-artistic works in the true sense are written with a deep consideration of specific historical realities. Textured images may be included only based on the requirements for the artwork. For example, in history education, when studying the topic "The struggle of the people of Central Asia against the Greek-Macedonian invaders", by getting acquainted with the novel "Sogdiyona" by the writer Yavdat Ilyasov, the student has a broader idea of the historical reality. can be[3:330]. By reading the novel, the student develops a sense of military patriotism based on the heroic struggle of Spitamen, who fought for the freedom of the Motherland.

Also, in the process of studying the "Invasion of Genghis Khan" from "History of Uzbekistan", students will learn with special interest the bravery of Temur Malik and Jalaluddin Manguberdi in the fight against the enemy. In order to further increase students' interest in studying the historical reality, assign the reading of the part of the book "Jalaluddin Manguberdi" called "Between Grass and Water"[4:26-30] and excerpts from Mirmuhsin's novel "Timur Malik" as independent work. and preparation of educational projects and presentations by students is appropriate [6].

Based on the above considerations, it can be said that if a student learns the main scientific evidence from historical sources and manuals, he will enrich his historical thinking by realizing its essence and importance through artistic works. Because the textbooks are written on the basis of a specific program, they have little opportunity to cover all the details of the historical reality. For example, in the "History of Uzbekistan" there is information about the "Sarbador movement", which was active in Samarkand in 1365-1366 and manifested a patriotic movement. In the process of studying the subject, in order for the students not to be limited by the information in the textbook, the independent reading of the historical novel "Warlords" written by the writer Muhammad Ali serves to fill the gap about this historical reality [7].

Reading and studying the works of not only Uzbek but also foreign writers on our national history will develop in them the skills of informational and

analytical thinking based on the comparative study and analysis of information on a certain historical process. For example, by reading the new novel "Amir Temur" by the Azerbaijani writer Yunus Oguz dedicated to Master Amir Temur, the student will have the opportunity to get acquainted with thoughts and historical facts that cannot be found in other works [9].

Shuningdek, jahon tarixini o'rganish jarayonida talabalar o'rta asrlar davlatlarida amalga oshirilgan urushlar va qo'zg'olonlar bilan tanishib borishar ekan, ularning ongida «Nega o'rta asrlarda va umuman insoniyat tarixida bunchalik urushlar ko'p bo'lgan ekan?!» degan savol tug'iladi. O'qituvchi mazkur savolga javob berishda O'tkir Hoshimovning «Daftar hoshiyasidagi bitiklar» asarida keltirilgan quyidagi qatradan javob sifatida foydalanishi mumkin: «Insoniyat tarixi – urushlar tarixidan iborat. Ertaklarda – urush. Dostonlarda – urush. Kitoblarda – urush. Kinolarda – urush... Tabaqalar urushi. Fuqarolar urushi. Mamlakatlar urushi. Jahon urushi. Olimlarning hisob-kitoblariga qaraganda so'nggi olti ming yil ichida Yer kurrasida 5700 marta urush bo'lgan ekan. (Mayda-chuyda qabilalar janjali bu hisobga kirmaydi)....» [10:21].

Bo'lajak tarix o'qituvchilarida informatsion-analitik kompetentlikni rivojlantirishga doir mustaqil faoliyatni tashkil etishda tarixiy manba bilan ishlashga doir guruhviy ish shakllarini qo'llash yaxshi samara beradi. Ma'lumki, boshqalarga o'rgatganda o'zing hamma narsani osonroq o'rganasan. Bir-biriga o'rgatish strategiyasi ana shundan kelib chiqqan, u barcha talabalarga o'qituvchining o'rnida bo'lish va boshqalarni tarixiy manba ustida ishlashga yo'naltirish imkoniyatini berish maqsadida ishlab chiqilgan. Axboriy matn bilan ishlaganda, bu strategiyani qo'llash yaxshi natija beradi.

CONCLUSION

The future history teacher takes historical evidence from information given in secondary sources, fragments from primary sources (rock inscriptions, works of historians, legends, narratives). However, working on these resources requires special training, special abilities and skills from the student. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to create an idea about the importance of sources in them. That is, any historical source, regardless of its level, is considered a huge historical monument and reflects the essence of its time. In other words, the source embodies historical, social, political, and spiritual reality. After all, any source is a reflection of the essence of the content and dominant ideas of its time. At the same time, it is necessary to establish in future history teachers the point of view that real life always has a wider meaning than any evidence,

document or source. Considering that future history teachers are working with the source, the socio-political process, the realities that have arisen as a result of it, and its logic, content and essence are wider than the source, no matter how complete it is, it is relative. should be taught not to forget that.

In short, the goals and tasks of developing the informational-analytical competence of future history teachers, the content of teaching, the design and planning of students' knowledge capabilities in accordance with the expected results guarantee the methodological effectiveness of this process.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan strategy. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2021.
2. Ibrohimov A. We, the Uzbeks... Reflections on the foundations of our national statehood. - T.: Sharq, 1999.
3. Ilyasov Y. Sogdiya. - T.: Sharq, 1994.
4. Jorayev N. Theoretical foundations of the philosophy of history. - T.: Ma'naviyat, 2008.
5. Mavrulov A. Education of a spiritually mature person. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2008.
6. Mirmukhsin. Timur Malik. - T.: Sharq, 1996.
7. Muhammad Ali. Soldiers. - T.: Publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam, 2009.
8. Yoldoshev S., Usmanov M., Karimov R. Western European philosophy of the new and newest era. - T.: Sharq, 2002.
9. Yunus Oguz. Amir Temur. - T.: New age generation, 2013.
10. Hashimov O'. Inscriptions on the border of the notebook. - T.: Sharq, 2001.

